

Maximum yields of 3.0 and 2.6 t/ha were recorded for these treatments. Mancozeb and Kitazin 48%, used in fol-

iar application, were most useful (Table 2).

Mancozeb was effective used as seed

dressing or foliar spray. Thiram as seed dressing and Kitazin 48% as spray effectively reduced grain infection. *h*

Efficacy of certain fungitoxicants against rice stem rot

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Stem rot, caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt. (*Leptosphaeria salvinii* Catt), is one of the most common rice diseases in Uttar Pradesh and in other Indian rice-growing areas. Farm workers have estimated grain weight losses ranging from

Efficacy of fungicides against stem rot disease and improved paddy grain yield, Agra College, India.

Fungicide	Dose	Disease control ^a (%)	Increased grain yield over control (kg/ha)
Kitazin 17% G	1 kg/ha	78.8	55.8
Dichlozoline	1 kg/ha	70.6	51.2
Thiabendazole	0.15%	61.7	40.2
Kausamine	0.10%	45.5	30.5
Edifenphos	0.1%	31.6	22.6

^aDisease incidence in control was 40.2%.
 $\% \text{ disease} = \frac{\% \text{ disease in control} - \text{control}}{\text{control}} \times 100.$

5 to 80%. These statistics prompted researchers to field-test fungicidal control methods for the disease.

During the 1978-79 wet season five fungicides (see table) were tested on susceptible variety Jhona 349 for their ability to control stem rot. Fields were sprayed 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting. Spray was directed to plant clumps at water level.

Kitazin 17% and dichlozoline were most effective in controlling the disease. Other effective fungicides, in descending order, were thiabendazole, Kausamine, and edifenphos. *h*

Pest management and control INSECTS

Boot leaf and spikelet damage in rice by whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino

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Rice whorl maggots *Hydrellia* spp. (Diptera: Ephydriidae) damage leaves during tillering stage. Flag leaf and occasional damage to developing grains are recorded, but no information on damage in late crop growth is available. During 1980 rabi widespread boot leaf and spikelet damage was noted on the AICRIP farm in Hyderabad. When

Dissected panicles from boot stage showing whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* damage to spikelet (left). A closer view of a shriveled spikelet and the maggot is on right.

Whorl maggot damage at different crop growth stages, AICRIP, 1979-80.^a

Treatment	Early leaf damage (%)			Late damage (1980 rabi)		
	1979 rabi, 40 DT	1979 kharif, 20 DT	1980 rabi, 30 DT	Tillers with boot leaf damage (%) 80 DT	Damaged spikelets/affected panicle in boot (no.) 80 DT	Damage panicle (%) 93 DT
No protection	15.9	8.3	26.0	4.4	6.8	5.8
Sprayed ^b on 15 and 55 DT	15.5	8.9	21.9	2.9	8.1	5.7
Sprayed ^b every 10 days	8.9	1.9	25.3	1.6	4.5	3.3

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bQuinalphos @ 0.5 kg a.i./ha.

booting stage tillers were dissected, maggots were observed to be feeding on spikelets (see figure). After emergence the affected panicles showed damage (shriveled spikelets) caused by the pest.

Whorl maggot damage to Jaya variety, under different protection treat-

ments, during three consecutive seasons is presented in the table. Damaged leaves in the vegetative stage (20 to 40 days after transplanting (DT) ranged from 8.3-26% in unprotected treatments. During 1980 rabi, 1.6-4.4% tillers with boot leaf damage were observed at 80

DT in different treatments. In affected boots 4.5-8.1% spikelets per panicle were injured. Damage in emerged panicles at 93 DT ranged from 3.3 to 5.8%. Insecticidal treatments at 10-day intervals reduced late damage symptoms more than other treatments. *h*

Water striders: new predators of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers in the Philippines

Alberto T. Barrion, research assistant, and James A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology, Department, IRRI

A 1981 survey of the rice field aquatic habitat on the IRRI farm revealed four species of water striders (Hemiptera: Gerridae) (see figure and table). Field and laboratory observations showed these water striders preyed on leafhop-

pers (*Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, *Cofana spectra*, *Recilia dorsalis*, and *Exitianus indicus*) and planthoppers (*Nilaparvata lugens*, *Sogatella, furcifera*, *Sogatodes pusanus*, and *Harmalia* sp.) that fell on the water.

Adult water striders *Limnognonoss fossarum* (A, female), *L. nitidus* (B, female), *Rheumatogonoss* sp. (C, male), and *Rhagadotarsus* sp. (D, female).

Characters of rice field-inhabiting gerrids, IRRI 1981.

Character	<i>Limnognonoss</i>		<i>Rheumatogonoss</i> sp.	<i>Rhagadotarsus</i> sp.
	<i>Fossarum</i> (F.)	<i>Nitidus</i> (Mayr)		
Total body length (mm)				
Male	8.88	8.16	5.66	No male insect collected
Female	10.88	9.0	7.33	4.83
Body appearance	Long and slender	Long and slender	Slightly shorter and thinner	Short to slightly oval
Length of middle and hind femora compared to body length	Shorter	Shorter	Longer	Shorter
Inner margin of eyes		Concave	Concave	Convex
Posterior lobe of pronotum	With yellow longitudinal band	Without band	Without band	Without band
Posterior 2/3 of middle tibia	Without thick hairs	Without thick hairs	With thick hairs	Without thick hairs
Shape of posterior end of abdomen	Bluntly pointed	Bluntly pointed	Blunt to slightly pointed	Pointed or spinelike